

LINGUISTIC FEATURES OF MORPHOLOGY IN THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Annotation

Morphology is the systematic study of morphemes, the smallest unit of grammar. Two types of morphological operations in English are inflection and derivation. English words can be grouped into two morphological classes: Base words and derived words. The two common word building processes are two viz. suffixes, prefixes. Other means are modifying the base/stem/root, no change of form, Compounding, Conversion, Back formation, Clipping, Blending, Acronyms, Reduplication. The advanced concepts related to this are further taken up for discussion.

Key words: Language, features, Morphology, Linguistic, description, morphemes, etymology, discussion, allomorph.

Introduction

Just as *etymology* (the study of the origin of words) and *phonology* (the study of the sounds of a language) are relevant in the description of language in terms of words, *morphology*, the systematic study of morphemes (the smallest unit of grammar), is significant. Morphemes are taken into consideration based on two essential factors.

1. They cannot be split into smaller morphemes.
2. It is a word or a part of word that has meaning.

Hence, in the word

- *unhappiness*: there are three parts; un-happy-ness (3),
- *unlikely*: there are three parts; un-like-ly (3),

- *pitiful*: there are two parts; pity-ful (2),
- *unjustifiable*: there are three parts; un-justify-able (3)
- *antidisestablishmentarianism*: there are six parts; anti-dis-establishment-arian-ism (6)

Before we pass on to the discussion of this particular section, let us have a quick recap of certain concepts and terms which you have already been introduced:

1. **Morpheme**: The word morpheme (consisting of two morphemes) is derived from the Greek word ‘morph’ meaning form/shape.
2. **Allomorphs**: Just as phonemes have allophones, morphemes have allomorphs. For example /-z/ /-s/ /-iz/ are phonologically conditioned allomorphs of the English plural morphemes, as in dogs, cats, horses. When we can explain in phonological terms why one particular allomorph of a morpheme occurs rather than another, we call it ‘regular’. But when we specify the actual morphemes to which the allomorph to which the allomorph attaches and indicate the special form of that allomorph, then we have ‘irregular’ morphological conditioning. For example the plural forms of English words such as man (*men*), goose (*geese*), child (*children*)
3. **Base**: A base is any morpheme or combination of morphemes to which one can attach either an inflectional suffix or derivational suffix. E.g. hot: hotter; boy-boys; boy- boyhood.
4. **Class changing**: It means effecting a change of word class when the affix is added to a stem. E.g. Clever-cleverness (adjective to noun)
5. **Class maintaining**: It means, when added to a stem, the affix does not change the word class of the stem. E.g. Undo-do (both are verbs).
6. **Lexeme**: In linguistics, lexeme is the fundamental unit of the lexicon (word stock) of a language. In Corpus linguistics, lexemes are referred to as “lemmas”. Laugh, laughed, laughing are all forms of the lexeme “laugh”

7. **Inflectional marking:** This occurs among the various words that compose a lexeme. E.g. dog, dogs, dog's, dogs'
8. **Derivational marking:** This creates one lexeme form another. E.g. kind-**unkind**; good- **goodness**.
9. **Stem:** A stem is any morpheme or combination of morphemes to which an inflectional suffix may be attached. 'Cat' is a stem of 'cats'
10. **Free morpheme:** It can occur as a word by itself. E.g. boy, run, happy
11. **Bound morpheme:** It can never occur by itself. E.g. -s in cats; -ish in **boyish**
12. **Prefix:** A prefix precedes a free morpheme. E.g. kind-**unkind**; like-**dislike**
13. **Suffix:** A suffix follows a free morpheme. Kind-kind**ness**; derive-**derivation**
14. **Null morpheme:**In morpheme-based morphology, a null morpheme is a morpheme that is realized by a phonologically null affix (an empty string of phonological segments). In simpler terms, a null morpheme is an "invisible" affix. It's also called zero morpheme. The null morpheme is represented as either the figure zero (0), the empty set symbol \emptyset .
15. **Clitics:** These "words" are like separate words in terms of how they combine with other words. English makes use of clitics separately, but uses the special "apostrophe" separator for some clitics, such as the reduced forms of *is*, *have* and *would* ('s 've 'd), and possessive 's.

Conclusion

The morphology of the English language is a part of English grammar which studies the structure of the English word, its components and functions and the

formation of the word. The English morphology is studying the word's root, affixes, suffixes, bases, inflections and phonemes.

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